

Preprint of Crego, A., Yela, J. R., & Ozores-Pérez, R. (2024). **A map of living: Moving through the variations of life with the guidance of metaphors.** *Journal of Contextual Behavioral Science*, 31, 100718. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcbs.2023.100718>

A map of living: moving through the variations of life with the guidance of metaphors.

Abstract

Metaphors are commonly used in psychotherapy, especially in Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT). Moreover, people use metaphors spontaneously in their everyday lives when trying to understand and make sense of complex issues. Relational Frame Theory (RFT) allows an analysis of metaphors as relating relations, where establishing coordination between a more concrete or familiar semantic domain with a more challenging target domain has pragmatic effects. A total of 806 Spanish-speaking participants were asked to provide a metaphor about life and to explain how they understood this metaphor. Their responses were analysed using reflexive Thematic Analysis (TA). The RFT and contributions from the cognitive linguistics approach to metaphors were used to interpret the patterns identified in the discourse on life metaphors. Participants' metaphors were organised into four themes: (1) recognition of variation in life, (2) attempts to make sense of variation in life, (3) problems with variation in life, and (4) evaluation of life as essentially positive or negative. Metaphors to recognise the multiplicity of events within life use “container”-related source-networks. Meaning in life is denoted through using networks connected with “movement toward a destination”, “human/natural development”, “fiction”, and “game and sports”, whereas metaphors involving disruptions in such patterns of change denote meaninglessness. Metaphors may also use particular qualities of entities and objects to signal positive and negative aspects of life. A variety of experiences connected with the source-networks of metaphors may be involved in the transfer of stimulus functions to the target-network “life”.

Qualitative analysis of life metaphors from the RFT perspective offers valuable insights on how metaphors function in everyday life and how they can be used in clinical work.

Key words: metaphors, meaning in life, Relational Frame Theory, Acceptance and Commitment Therapy, Thematic Analysis.

Introduction

Human language achieves some of its properties thanks to the incorporation of metaphorical uses (Ellison & Reinöhl, 2022; Lerman, 1991; Smith & Höfler, 2017). Moreover, many everyday expressions actually have a metaphorical origin (Barclay, 1997; Goatly, 1997). To a large extent, the language we use to describe private events consists of metaphors constructed from events in our external environment (Skinner, 1945, 1957; Törneke, 2010).

Analysing this metaphorical substratum of common language is interesting because it provides information about how complex and abstract concepts are constructed. Sometimes, knowing the basic metaphor underlying such concepts is clarifying, since metaphor usually refers us to a more concrete and even corporeal experience (Kövecses, 2010; Lakoff & Johnson, 1980). Life, with its complexity, is one of the semantic domains about which speakers have generated a large number of metaphors. The wide range of life metaphors used in literature and in everyday conversations is no accident. The use of metaphors occurs especially when individuals are faced with the need to make sense of events and circumstances that are beyond what can be encompassed by the literality of language. We are forced to generate metaphors where we are faced with a complex, abstract, problematic, difficult to communicate experience whose meaning is uncertain (Bowdle & Gentner, 2005; Gentner & Bowdle, 2008). To use a simile, on these occasions the metaphor acts like a map. We use a more familiar semantic domain to understand a more complex one, which can be done by bridging the two domains. Such bridges are features of the source domain that are easily transferable to the target domain. In this sense, according to Relational Frame Theory (RFT), a metaphor involves establishing a frame of coordination between two sets of relations through a physical or formal property, dimension, or relation (Stewart & Barnes-Holmes, 2001; Stewart et al., 2001).

Knowing the metaphors' structure informs us about semantic relationships (i.e., how we relate relations, from an RFT perspective) present in our language and contributes to explain how

a person operates when reasoning using analogies. Moreover, metaphors are also interesting from a pragmatic point of view. The use of metaphors influences the way we think about our social environment, reason and make decisions (Thibodeau & Boroditsky, 2011, 2013, 2015). Using metaphors helps us make sense of and interpret complex issues. This idea is particularly interesting when referring to life metaphors, as the use of one or another metaphor can influence how and when individuals experience their lives as meaningful (Baldwin et al., 2018). Life metaphors also have connections with the perception of meaning in life and variables related to well-being and mental health. For example, Crego et al. (2022) found that eudaimonic metaphors, such as “life is a journey” or “life is a treasure”, were associated with higher levels of happiness and meaningfulness, and lower levels of experiential avoidance, anxiety, depression and mental health problems. Other metaphors that were related to the perception of uncertainty, such as “life is a maze” or “life is a lottery”, were associated with lower happiness and meaning in life, higher experiential avoidance, and higher presence of mental health symptoms. Evidence on the effects of metaphors’ use also comes from experimental studies. Baldwin et al. (2018) have revealed that using life metaphors such as “life is a journey” can increase the perception of meaning, especially among those individuals experiencing low life coherence and those with a weak meaning framework. Even when metaphors are used in more specific domains, such as academic life, the use of different metaphors has effects on motivation and commitment to goal-directed action in these areas (Landau et al., 2014). Therefore, the use of certain life metaphors is not neutral but has psychological implications and is linked to the experience of continuity (vs. fragmentation), purpose (vs. pointlessness) and value (vs. worthlessness) in life (Landau, 2018).

RFT explains the pragmatic character of metaphors through the idea of transformation of functions. Metaphors work by effectively transferring features that are very evident in one event to a different event (Törneke, 2010). Interestingly, this operation where a coordination frame is established has remarkable effects. Some functions of the target domain may be transformed as a

result of understanding it in terms of the source domain (Stewart & Barnes-Holmes, 2001; Stewart et al., 2001).

The cognitive and pragmatic effects of metaphors made them a commonly used tool in psychotherapy, especially in the Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT) (Foody et al., 2014; McCurry & Hayes, 1992; Stoddard & Afari, 2014; Törneke, 2017, 2020). From the ACT point of view, metaphors are a tool to bypass verbal traps, promote psychological flexibility and suggest to clients more flexible and open ways of acting (Stoddard & Afari, 2014; Törneke, 2010; Villate et al., 2014). Through therapeutic uses of metaphors, clients may understand challenging events from a more experiential approach, rather than intellectually (Ramírez et al., 2021). The potential effects of metaphor use have also been tested experimentally. For example, pain tolerance in the cold-pressor task is increased by the use of metaphors that include common physical properties with the experienced pain and specify appetitive augmentals (i.e. values) (Criollo et al., 2018; Ruiz et al., 2020; Sierra et al., 2016), and by metaphors where the individuals are asked to imagine themselves as the protagonists of the story and prompts for relational elaboration are provided (Ramírez et al., 2021).

The present study

In this study we try to analyse the metaphors that a large sample of Spanish speakers use to refer to life, as well as the discourse they use to explain these metaphors. Our objectives with this qualitative material are twofold. First, we aim to identify the thematic patterns around which metaphorical discourse about life can be organised. Second, we will try to understand how metaphors about life are structured and how they transform the stimulus functions of the target-network “life”. In approaching this second task, as will become clear later, both RFT and modern cognitive linguistics may shed light on the connection between the semantic (thematic) and functional aspects of metaphorical language.

Method

Participants

The participants were 806 individuals (83 % female), with an age range from 18 to 81 years (Mean = 40.74; *Sd* = 16.85). The sample included 18 Spanish-speaking countries, with the largest participation coming from Venezuela (30.1%), Argentina (21.1%), Colombia (12.2%), Mexico (11.2%), Nicaragua (7.1%), Spain (3.2%), Paraguay (2.6%), Bolivia (2.1%) and Guatemala (2.0%). More than half of the sample had a university education, either at graduate (45.7%) or postgraduate (12.9%) level. Participants with high school education represented 17.7% and 18.7% had received professional training. Only 5% of participants had basic studies. Regarding employment status, 34.9% of the participants indicated that they were employed, 21.8% unemployed, and 12.9% retired. Students represented 21.1% of the sample and people in other employment situations (e.g. temporary medical leave, unpaid domestic work, etc.) accounted for 9.3%.

Instruments and Procedures

A qualitative questionnaire was used to elicit responses from participants that were indicative of the metaphors they use to refer to life. One of the items asked participants "If you were asked, life is like _____, how would you answer?" Participants were then given a short space to complete the sentence "Life is like _____" using a word or short expression. This item was designed by Hoffman and Acosta-Orozco (2015) and was previously used in research on metaphors in the Spanish-speaking context (Hoffman et al., 2015, 2021). After completing this item, participants were asked to explain their answer, while providing them with a large space where they could write their response, and no character limit. The questionnaire also included questions concerning the socio-demographic characteristics of the participants. Data collection was carried out by means of an online survey designed using Google Forms, following Braun et

al. (2021). Prior to completing the survey, participants read the informed consent document, which provided a general introduction to the broader research project of which this study is a part, focused on the relationship between the experience of meaning in life and psychological well-being. Participants were also informed of privacy and anonymity guarantees concerning their responses. Participation in this study was voluntary, with participants receiving no compensation for completing the questionnaire. Data collection took place from July to September 2021. This research was approved by the Ethics Committee of the [blinded name of Institution] (Minutes of the meeting 28/05/2021).

Qualitative analysis

The participants' responses were analysed following reflexive Thematic Analysis (TA) methodology for qualitative analysis, as developed by Braun and Clarke (2006, 2012, 2022). TA is a widely used method in psychology that seeks to identify, analyse and report patterns (themes) within a qualitative data set. The TA procedure has six phases: 1) Familiarisation with the data; 2) Generating initial codes; 3) Searching for themes or patterns; 4) Reviewing themes and generating a thematic 'map' of the analysis; 5) Generating definitions and names for each theme; and 6) Producing the report. The 15-point checklist for good reflexive TA, developed by Braun and Clarke (2022), was taken into account.

Moreover, the reflexive character of TA requires the practice of critical reflection on the researchers' own role, practices and processes. Here, we have followed an inductive approach to the data, according to which themes identified are strongly connected to the data themselves (Braun & Clarke, 2006, 2022). The level of analysis focused on the semantic dimension of the data, which in the TA process involves a progression from description, with data being organised and summarised to show patterns, to interpretation, where an attempt to discuss the significance of the themes and their broader meanings and implications is made (Braun & Clarke, 2006). For the interpretative part, we connected the identified themes with contributions from Relational Frame

Theory (Barnes-Holmes & Harte, 2022; Hayes & Wilson, 1994; Hayes et al., 2001; Stewart & Barnes-Holmes, 2001; Törneke, 2010) and cognitive linguistics approaches to metaphors (Gibbs, 2006; Gibbs & Matlock, 2008; Kövecses, 2010; Lakoff, 1990, 1993; Lakoff & Johnson, 1980, 1999; Müller, 2017, 2019).

In our study, we conducted a collaborative analysis process (Braun & Clarke, 2022), with all researchers actively participating at all stages. The initial coding of the material was conducted by one researcher and then reviewed independently by two other researchers. Following this review, consensus was reached on a final coding of the material provided by the participants. QDA Miner Lite software (Provalis Research, Montreal, Canada) was used for coding and managing the participants' responses. The search for themes to organise the meanings present in the set of responses, the review of themes, and the creation of a thematic map was developed by discussing different thematic structuring possibilities until consensus was reached.

Results

The participants' responses were organised around four broad themes (Figure 1). A first thematic grouping focused on considering life as essentially variation, change, and transformation. Interestingly, a second theme focused on metaphors that try to structure this variation, without denying it. The third theme developed from the participants' discourse reflects the opposite of seeing patterns in life. Finally, a fourth theme refers to general evaluations of life in positive or negative terms.

Theme 1. Life as variation, change or transformation.

In this first theme, metaphors emphasise that life is multiple and diverse (Table 1). Here, the participants simply note the variety of events that may happen in life and its multiform character. Life, in this sense, would have numerous nuances, layers, faces, etc. However, these metaphors say nothing about how these variations originate, develop or about their purpose.

Metaphors that emphasise the transience of life can also be seen as a variant of this theme of variation and change. Focusing on ephemerality or impermanence is another indication of seeing life as a changing process.

Theme 2. Finding patterns within variation

The second group of metaphors is organised around the idea that life is structured, ordered or patterned change (Table 2). These meanings are presented in the participants' metaphors in various ways, with an underlying common idea: life involves a starting point, a development in which various vicissitudes or events may occur, and a destination or end point. Life is thus seen as an organised process, where variation can be ordered according to this general scheme. These are metaphors embracing the idea of variation, and even assuming that variation can be problematic at times; however, changes and transformations are intelligible within a wider structure or scheme of staged change. Indeed, vicissitudes and changes -even those that may be of a more aversive nature- may be necessary, insofar as they are part of the process of movement (e.g. the path) or a phase of development leading to the achievement of the final state.

In particular, we have identified three ways in which the idea that life is structured change takes shape. A group of metaphors equates life to a movement from a current point to a destination (Subtheme 2.1). This is the case in metaphors where life is seen as a journey, a road, or where elements are taken from these semantic domains, as for example is done by equating life to a means of transport.

Other metaphors are drawn from the source domains involving human developmental processes or natural developmental processes (Subtheme 2.2). Examples are metaphors that refer to life as learning, or to elements related to it, such as school, classroom, teachers, etc. These metaphors are modelled on the image of a process of human development involving an initial starting point, transformation, change or growth, and the attainment of a new state of greater

maturity or complexity. The idea that life is a process of patterned change is also built on the model of developmental processes of natural phenomena. Living beings go through a process of birth, growth and development, followed by decline and death. But also other natural phenomena, such as the course of the seasons, follow a model of patterned change that can be taken as a reference in the construction of this type of metaphor.

Finally, participants also structured the idea of life as transformation and change through a series of stages by assimilating life to fiction or games and sports (Subtheme 2.3). Such metaphors, in a sense, use fiction, structured games and sports as a simulation or representation of life. For example, fiction, such as novels, short stories, films, or plays, are creations involving characters with certain traits and motivations that go through episodes, plots and subplots where events are depicted in a comprehensible way. Here, works of fiction can be seen as models or simulations in relation to a wide variety of relationships between characters, social roles and socio-cultural norms, presenting obstacles and conflicts, ways of coping with life events, psychological transformations of characters, etc. Similarly, play and sport can be seen as a representation of life with its norms, social roles, relations of cooperation and conflict, objectives and goals, values, etc. Both fiction and play and sport can serve as an example, or as training for life, and in this sense simulate or imitate it. Again, in these fictional or game/sport-based, metaphors of the variations of life are structured in a beginning, development and end. For example, narratives are frequently organised in a three-part structure. In this classic structure, the work begins with an initial situation (introduction or opening of the narrative, presentation of the context and the personalities), passes through a development of the story where the protagonist goes through a series of vicissitudes and finally reaches a resolution, i.e. the end of the story where the main plot and the subplots are concluded. And again, the stories do not hide or avoid variety. Characters can be exposed to favourable and unfavourable events, go through various obstacles, and transform themselves in the course of the story. Narratives can also fit into different genres,

such as comedy, drama, thriller, horror, etc. in an ever-widening range of options. But this variety is integrated into the structure of the story. Overall, the narrative must be plausible and comprehensible in order to work. Variation and change must be coherent and consistent; for instance, there must be a link between the events, the characters must act for reasons and motives intelligible to the audience, etc. Similarly, in play and sport there is a starting point and an end of the game. In between, the development of the game works on variety, e.g. there are moments of advantage and disadvantage, there is conflict between rivals competing to achieve their goals, unexpected events occur (mistakes in the game, injuries in the sport, etc.). But there are also rules of the game, rewards and punishments, and referees, systems for making decisions (e.g. to determine who wins), there is coordination of roles and division of labour in team games, and of course, there is a purpose of the game (the goal to be achieved in order to win).

Structured games and sports are therefore forms in which variation is at once recognised, allowed, and patterned. There is a further connection between fiction and games/sports. In a sense, they are both “performances” or “shows” that attract attention, entertain, generate all kinds of emotions, and include social elements. Games and sport often have a component of theatricality and representation of a social ritual while fiction often has a playful character, whether understood as mere amusement or as an intellectual exercise.

Theme 3. Variation in life as a problem

The third theme refers to problems or difficulties arising from the changing nature of life (Table 3). Theme 3 groups together a set of meanings presenting life as a disorganised, unstructured array of events, in clear opposition to Theme 2. For participants using these metaphors, life events may lack a clear purpose (Subtheme 3.1), be random and unpredictable (Subtheme 3.2), unknowable or enigmatic (Subtheme 3.3), beyond one's control (Subtheme 3.4), or have a destructive character associated with conflict, isolation/separation and chaos (Subtheme 3.5).

Theme 3 is particularly interesting because, in general, the idea of dis-order and disruption of the structuring of life builds on the paradigms of metaphors that were presented in Theme 2. Here, metaphors related to the semantic domains of movement, human or natural development, and fiction and games/sports appear again in Theme 3. However, some features from these semantic domains are now selected to convey the idea of de-structuring and problems with change. The previous paradigms used for structuring variation are now altered and broken in various ways, in order to reflect that life is something dis-ordered.

Remarkably, the problems with variation in life (i.e. Subthemes 3.1 to 3.5) are not usually reported in isolation, but are often interconnected. For example, a haphazard life may also be judged as absurd (purposeless), unfathomable, and beyond one's control. Thus, a metaphor reflecting the rupture of structure (i.e., life is a maze, life is a prison, etc.) can communicate several interconnected meanings.

Theme 4. The evaluation of life as essentially positive or negative

Theme 4 refers to assessments of life, either in positive (Subtheme 4.1) or negative (Subtheme 4.2) terms. This theme groups together metaphors usually presenting a rather simple form, in which an appetitive or aversive property or characteristic of an object is selected to indicate, respectively, the essentially positive or negative quality of life. Frequently, although not exclusively, the semantic domains used in Theme 4 metaphor construction come from the realm of nature and food, focusing on sensory qualities. For example, life is equated to something either pleasant or unpleasant to the sight, to the taste, etc.

Discussion

Using RFT and cognitive linguistics to interpret the discourse on life metaphors

The patterns of meaning identified in the thematic analysis can be interpreted in the light of the contributions on language and cognition from Relational Frame Theory and modern

linguistics. In particular, these approaches may be useful to analyse how life metaphors are structured, identify what aspects of the source domains are connected with the target domain of “life”, and how the transformation of functions in the relational network of life occurs.

As mentioned, RFT considers metaphors as an example of complex verbal behaviour in which relations among relations are established (Barnes-Holmes & Harte, 2022; Stewart & Barnes-Holmes, 2004). In metaphors, a frame of coordination is established between the source domain from which the metaphor is drawn and the target domain of the metaphor, whose function is to be transformed by being approached in terms of the source domain. These elements were already present in the construction of our question to the participants. In the expression "Life is _____", the verb "is" functions as a relational cue (Crel) that is signalling a relation of coordination or equivalence. For instance, when a participant answers "Life is a strawberry -I love strawberries", he/she is coordinating the relational network of the source domain "strawberries" with the target domain “life”. As a result, appetitive or approximation functions (Cfunc) present in the source (e.g. based on pleasant sensations, taste, etc.) are transferred to the term “life”. This RFT-based analysis is applicable to other metaphors. For instance, establishing a coordination frame between a “labyrinth” and “life” may transfer aversive functions from the source network to the target network, based on meanings connected to labyrinths such as uncertainty, absence of safe paths, getting lost, etc.

An interesting question is how the relational network of the source domain transforms the functions of the relational network of the target, and particularly how it occurs in the case of metaphors about life. Recent RFT-based research on the effectiveness of metaphors offers useful insights. As Ramirez et al. (2021) have shown, experiential aspects are of great importance for the transformation of functions through the use of metaphors. A metaphor is more effective when the person vividly contacts the emotional functions present in the symbolic context created by the metaphor, compared to merely intellectual exposure to the metaphor. For instance, asking

individuals to imagine herself/himself as the protagonist of the story instead of presenting the metaphor in the third person (Ramírez et al., 2021) and including physical properties common to the participant's discomfort in the metaphor (Criollo et al., 2018; Ruiz et al., 2020; Sierra et al., 2016) may enhance the transformation of functions.

In a similar vein, cognitive linguistics suggests that metaphor construction is grounded in a variety of physical, bodily and cultural experiences (Casasanto, 2014; Lakoff & Johnson, 1980). Particular emphasis has been placed on the role of embodied experience in relation to metaphors (Gibbs et al., 2004; Gibbs, 2006; Gibbs & Matlock, 2008; Lakoff & Johnson, 1999). According to this view, the understanding of a metaphorical expression would be underpinned by the mental recreation of bodily processes and experiences associated with situations related to the source domain, which would activate a schema (e.g., SOURCE-PATH-GOAL). Such a schema is transferred to a different domain (e.g. life) to provide some understanding of it. Recent developments consider that metaphoric meaning-making processes are dynamic and emerge from embodied interactivity, i.e. metaphorizing is grounded in inter-corporeal and inter-affective experiences embedded in interaction environments (Müller, 2019). More generally, Oatley (1999, 2001, 2016) has suggested that fictional stories (i.e. metaphors) may be considered as simulations that, when internalised, allows us to become more aware of the self, of other selves and to enhance our understanding of the social world.

The metaphors in Themes 1 (variation in life) and 4 (evaluation of life) establish equivalences between life and concrete objects (e.g., "Life is a box of chocolates" -variation-; "Life is a treasure" -positive evaluation-) or between life and concrete characteristics of certain phenomena (e.g. the transience of "a wind" or "a shooting star"-variation-; the discomfort of a "rainy day" -negative evaluation-). Here, ontological metaphors are used (Lakoff & Johnson, 1980). These metaphors attempt to assign a new ontological status - concrete and materialised - to an abstract, general, vaguely defined or not well delimited concept, such as "life". In ontological

metaphors the source domain is an object, entity, container or substance, through which the target is apprehended in terms of a tangible, manipulable experience (Kövecses, 2010; Lakoff & Johnson, 1980).

Despite the communalities, the construction of metaphors and the functions to be transformed into the target ("life") are different in Themes 1 and 4. In Theme 1, a coordination frame is established between "life" and source terms denoting "containers". For example, life is understood as a box (container) in which there are a variety of objects (chocolates), a meadow (container) comprising different kinds of grasses, colours, a variety of events, multiple sensory experiences, etc., or as a sky (container) inside which different atmospheric phenomena occur. In all these metaphors, the functions selected and transferred to the relational network of "life" are qualities such as diversity and multiplicity, derived from the varieties of experiences connected with such "containers". As a result, the abstract domain of "life" is viewed as the container delimiting a variety of events taking place inside. In Theme 1, "life" also appears in a frame of coordination with other sorts of objects and entities in metaphors to emphasise the transience of life. Here, concrete qualities of the object, such as its speed or fleeting nature, are transferred to the network of "life" (e.g., transience of a shooting star crossing the sky, the wind, or a flicker). In these metaphors, the abstract domain of "life" is delimited in relation to duration, in contrast to the container metaphor, where life was demarcated in terms of space.

In Theme 4 the construction of metaphors is based on selecting a property of the source object/entity with a positive or negative valence, a function that is transferred to the relational network of "life". For example, establishing a correspondence between a treasure or a gift (i.e. valuable objects) and "life" transfers appetitive functions related to our experience with such objects (e.g. joy, positive surprise, appreciation, etc.) to the relational network of the target. The appetitive functions transferred may be also grounded on sensory experiences, e.g., when linking "life" with "strawberries" (e.g., pleasant taste and smell, nice colours, etc.). The transfer of

aversive functions in Theme 4 uses the same metaphor constructions. Here, a negative quality of the source-object is selected; and again, the metaphor may trigger sensory experiences (e.g. disgust in the metaphor “life is a dog poo”, the discomfort of “a rainy day”, the “hardness” of life) and other experiences such as the strangeness or difficulty associated to some “things”.

According to Kövecses (2010), once an abstract experience has received an ontological status as a metaphorically reified entity, the target domain can be structured in more complex ways through other types of metaphors. Following Lakoff and Johnson (1980), structural metaphors widely enable the speaker to understand a semantic domain -i.e. "life"- in terms of the relatively rich knowledge structure of the source network. In this regard, what is selected to link the target and the source domains is not a specific quality of a particular object but a broader network of relations present in the source domain.

The metaphors in Theme 2 (making sense of variation) work by viewing “life” through the structure of a variety of source-networks denoting purposeful, coherent, comprehensible processes and movement. We have identified structuring paradigms that consider life as movement towards a destination (e.g. life is a journey), development in stages (e.g. viewing life as the life-cycle of a plant), fiction (e.g. life is a story), and life as play or sport (e.g. life is a chess game). Interestingly, these paradigms may incorporate a view of the self as a proactive agent (e.g. being the traveller who actively moves towards a destination/goal, or the author of a literary work). From an RFT perspective, appetitive functions (i.e., meaningfulness, predictability, understandability, self-efficacy, etc.) may be transferred to the relational network of "life", on the basis of the experiences connected with the source network (e.g., thoughts, emotions, bodily sensations, social experiences connected with travelling).

To a great extent, the metaphors included in Theme 3 (problems with variation) use the source-networks already present in Theme 2. For example, the movement-related paradigm also appears in Theme 3, but a destination-point is absent. The movement of life may be circular (e.g.

life is a carousel), go up and down (e.g. life is a roller coaster), with no clear direction (e.g. life is a maze or a dark tunnel), be unpredictable (e.g. life is a weathercock) or there may be a restriction of movement (e.g. life is a prison). In Theme 3 the fiction-related metaphors are used to suggest that the self is a mere puppet, giving a deterministic view of its role; not as an author, but merely as a character acting out a script. Other metaphors may also suggest the idea of the self as guilty or being punished (e.g. being imprisoned in life) and the individual as a lost person (e.g. being in a labyrinth). Similarly, the game-related network is used here to emphasise randomness and lack of control (e.g. life is a lottery) and extreme sports are selected as source-domain (e.g. life is a boxing match). From an RFT-based interpretation, aversive functions grounded on experiences like fear, lack of purpose, isolation, etc. may be transferred to the domain of “life” when the labyrinth, prison, war, and other metaphors are used.

The metaphors of Themes 2 and 3 are consistent with the Event Structure Metaphor (Lakoff, 1990, 1993), a network connecting conceptual metaphors that describe different aspects of events. In particular, the Event Structure Metaphor uses the relational network of “movement” to understand change in events. Metaphors clustered in the Event Structure Metaphor are, among others, “changes are movements”, “purposes are destinations”, “means are paths”, “purposeful action is directed motion toward a destination”, “long term purposeful activities are journeys” and on the problematic side, “impediments to action are impediments to motion”, “lack of purpose is lack of direction”, “lack of control over change is lack of control over movement”. The equivalence between change and movement is clear in some metaphors identified in Themes 2 (e.g. life is a journey) and 3 (e.g. life is a roller coaster). Moreover, the same equivalence could be implicit in other metaphors in Themes 2 and 3. For example, metaphors that structure life as a process of human or natural development, a work of fiction, a game and a sport may be translated into basic structures where there is a movement from an initial state (e.g. birth, presentation of the story, beginning of the game, etc.) to a final state (e.g. death, ending of a story, resolution of a

game) through a series of stages (phases of natural development, chapters of the fictional work, moves in a game).

Limitations and future research

This study has limitations which, at the same time, leave new lines of research open. Firstly, the participants' life metaphors were elicited using an item and an open-ended question asking them to explain the reported metaphor. While this method is an efficient way of collecting qualitative data (Braun et al., 2021), it would be interesting to conduct qualitative studies using interviews and more extensive qualitative questionnaires, so that participants could generate more complex narratives, either about the metaphorical understanding of life or, more generically, about the meaning of life. Moreover, it would be interesting to analyse metaphors about life in the contexts in which they are used, enacted and embedded, taking into account their multimodal (i.e. metaphors may be expressed in words, gestures, music, pieces of art, film, etc.) and dynamic (i.e. grounded in a process of interactive meaning-making) character (Müller, 2017).

Second, our study is focused on the analysis of metaphor-related discourse, but the discourse was not connected with other psychological aspects, such as well-being, mental health, one's own experience of meaning in life, or attitudes of openness or avoidance towards life. Although, in general, the metaphors used by participants may denote presence or absence of meaning, emotions towards life, and may even hint at attitudes towards oneself, it would be very interesting to collect qualitative material where participants reflect both on life metaphors and their connection with psychological aspects such as those mentioned above.

Research analysing the connection between the participants' discourse and their socio-demographic and cultural characteristics would be worth doing. For instance, it would be interesting to know whether women and men, people with different levels of education, or individuals with different occupations, ages and nationalities have a preference for different metaphors when it comes to understanding life. In this regard, previous literature has already

pointed to the importance of contextual factors in the use of metaphors (Benczes & Ságvári, 2018; Kövecses, 2005, 2015, 2017; Kuczok, 2016). This objective is beyond the aims of the present research, where the composition of the sample of participants is a limitation (e.g. overall, few men participated, some nationalities are underrepresented, etc.). The use of a combination of qualitative and quantitative strategies may also offer new perspectives on this topic.

Finally, a very compelling line of research is the analysis of the use of metaphors about life in specific domains, especially in the clinical setting.

Practical implications

The metaphor paradigms identified in the present study may help the clinician to generate a broader repertoire of metaphors from some basic structures. From an ACT-based approach, metaphors may be a tool to promote psychological flexibility and reduce experiential avoidance (Foody et al., 2014; Ramirez et al., 2021; Stoddard & Afari, 2014; Törneke, 2010, 2017, 2020). Moreover, research in RFT and cognitive linguistics has highlighted the importance of the experiential aspects of metaphors. Metaphors are language artefacts that create symbolic contexts in which exposure to experiences connected with the source domain are triggered. In this sense, metaphors may facilitate contact with challenging experiences through the transformation of stimulus functions of the initially problematic network in multiple ways. For instance, metaphors may provide the client with a clearer understanding of the experience, transform initially aversive functions into approaching motivation, and suggest new courses of behaviour.

The analysis of life metaphors is particularly relevant to work on the values-related dimension of therapeutic change from the ACT perspective. For instance, experiences of purpose, coherence and meaning in life may be enhanced by using metaphors grounded on the “movement towards a destination” and “patterned development” structures. In addition, appetitive functions (i.e. mattering, significance) can be transferred to the domain of “life” by establishing a coordination frame with sources such as “treasure”, “gift”, etc.

The metaphors used by a client may provide insights on how he/she assesses change in life and sees his/herself. For example, metaphors may reveal if the individual is the author or a powerless character in the story of his/her life, etc. Metaphors may be also informative about feelings of meaninglessness in life and even offer clues to identify what is implicit in this experience, such as the absence of an identifiable destination (life goals), interruptions in movement (obstacles encountered), stagnation and imprisonment (situations of social isolation), or unpredictability, lack of control, etc., as denoted by other metaphors. As Hayes (2017) metaphorically said, psychotherapists without metaphors would be like plumbers without tools.

References

- Baldwin, M., Landau, M. J., & Swanson, T. J. (2018). Metaphors can give life meaning. *Self and Identity, 17*(2), 163-193. <http://doi.org/10.1080/15298868.2017.1368696>
- Barclay, M. W. (1997). The metaphoric foundation of literal language: Toward a theory of the reification and meaning of psychological constructs. *Theory and Psychology, 7*, 355-372. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0959354397073004>
- Barnes-Holmes, D., & Harte, C. (2022). Relational frame theory 20 years on: The Odysseus voyage and beyond. *Journal of the Experimental Analysis of Behavior, 117*(2), 240-266. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jeab.733>
- Benczes, R. & Ságvári, B. (2018): Where metaphors really come from: Social factors as contextual influence in Hungarian teenagers' metaphorical conceptualizations of life. *Cognitive Linguistics 29*(1): 121-54. <http://doi.org/10.1515/cog-2016-0139>
- Bowdle, B. F., & Gentner, D. (2005). The career of metaphor. *Psychological Review, 112*(1), 193-216. <http://doi.org/10.1037/0033-295X.112.1.193>
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative research in psychology, 3*(2), 77-101. <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp063oa>
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2012). Thematic Analysis. In Cooper, H. E., Camic, P. M., Long, D. L., Panter, A. T., Rindskopf, D. E., & Sher, K. J. (Eds.), *APA handbook of research methods in psychology, Vol 2: Research designs: Quantitative, qualitative, neuropsychological, and biological* (pp.57-71). American Psychological Association. <https://doi.org/10.1037/13620-004>
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2022). *Thematic Analysis: A practical guide*. Sage Publications.

- Braun, V., Clarke, V., Boulton, E., Davey, L., & McEvoy, C. (2021). The online survey as a qualitative research tool. *International Journal of Social Research Methodology*, 24(6), 641-654. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13645579.2020.1805550>
- Casasanto, D. (2014). Experiential origins of mental metaphors: Language, culture, and the body. In M. Landau, M. D. Robinson, & B. P. Meier (Eds.), *The power of metaphor: Examining its influence on social life* (pp. 249-268). American Psychological Association. <https://doi.org/10.1037/14278-011>
- Crego, A., Yela, J. R., Ozores-Pérez, R., Riesco-Matías, P., & Gómez-Martínez, M. Á. (2022). Eudaimonic and Uncertainty Metaphors About Life are Associated with Meaningfulness, Experiential Avoidance, Mental Health and Happiness. *Journal of Happiness Studies*, 23(8), 4119-4146. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10902-022-00594-3>
- Criollo, A. B., Díaz-Muelle, S., Ruiz, F. J., & García-Martín, M. B. (2018). Common physical properties improve metaphor effect even in the context of multiple examples. *The Psychological Record*, 68(4), 513–523. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40732-018-0297-9>
- Ellison, T. M., & Reinöhl, U. (2022). Compositionality, Metaphor, and the Evolution of Language. *International Journal of Primatology*, 1-17. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10764-022-00315-w>
- Foody, M., Barnes-Holmes, Y., Barnes-Holmes, D., Törneke, N., Luciano, C., Stewart, I., & McEnteggart, C. (2014). RFT for clinical use: The example of metaphor. *Journal of Contextual Behavioral Science*, 3, 305-313. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcbs.2014.08.001>
- Gentner, D. & Bowdle, B.F. (2008). Metaphor as structure-mapping. In R. W. Gibbs (Ed.), *The Cambridge Handbook of Metaphor and Thought*. pp. 109-128. Cambridge University Press.
- Gibbs, R. W. (2006). Metaphor interpretation as embodied simulation. *Mind & Language*, 21, 434-458. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-0017.2006.00285.x>

- Gibbs, R. W., & Matlock, T. (2008). Metaphor, imagination, and simulation: Psycholinguistic evidence. In R. W. Gibbs (Ed.), *The Cambridge Handbook of Metaphor and Thought*. pp. 161-176. Cambridge University Press.
- Gibbs, R. W., Lima, P. L. C., & Francozo, E. (2004). Metaphor is grounded in embodied experience. *Journal of Pragmatics*, 36(7), 1189-1210.
<http://www.doi.org/10.1016/j.pragma.2003.10.009>
- Goatly, A. (1997). *The language of metaphors*. Routledge.
<https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203210000>
- Hayes, S.C. (2017). Foreword. In N. Törneke, *Metaphor in practice: A professional's guide to using the science of language in psychotherapy* (pp. vii-ix). New Harbinger Publications.
- Hayes, S. C., & Wilson, K. G. (1994). Acceptance and commitment therapy: Altering the verbal support for experiential avoidance. *The Behavior Analyst*, 17(2), 289-303.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/BF03392677>
- Hayes, S. C., Barnes-Holmes, D., & Roche, B. (Eds.) (2001). *Relational frame theory*. Kluwer Academic/ Plenum Publishers.
- Hoffman, E. & Acosta-Orozco, C. (2015). Life-metaphors among Colombian leadership students: Core values and educational implications. *College Student Journal*, 49, 438-446.
- Hoffman, E., Acosta-Orozco, C. & Compton, W.C. (2015). Life-metaphors among Colombian medical students: Uncovering core values and educational implications. *College Student Journal*, 49, 579-586.
- Hoffman, E., Acosta-Orozco, C., Compton, W. C., & Ortiz, F. A. (2021). Engineers' life metaphors: Assessing their core values and work engagement 7. *Alternatives in Psychology*, 45, 52-67.

- Kövecses, Z. (2005). *Metaphor in culture: Universality and variation*. Cambridge University Press.
- Kövecses, Z. (2010). *Metaphor: A practical introduction*. Oxford University Press.
- Kövecses, Z. (2015). *Where metaphors come from: Reconsidering context in metaphor*. Oxford University Press.
- Kövecses, Z. (2017). Context in cultural linguistics: The case of metaphor. In F. Sharifian (Ed.), *Advances in Cultural Linguistics* (pp. 307-323). Springer.
- Kuczok, M. (2016). Precious possession, war or journey? Conceptual metaphors for "life" in American English, Hungarian, and Polish. In B. Cetnarowska, M. Kuczok, M. Zabawa (Eds.), *Various dimensions of contrastive studies* (pp. 157-170). Wydawnictwo Uniwersytetu Śląskiego.
- Lakoff, G. (1990). The invariance hypothesis: Is abstract reason based on image-schemas? *Cognitive Linguistics, 1*, 39-74. <https://doi.org/10.1515/cogl.1990.1.1.39>
- Lakoff, G. (1993). The contemporary theory of metaphor. In A. Ortony (Ed.), *Metaphor and thought* (pp. 202–251). Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781139173865.013>
- Lakoff, G., & Johnson, M. (1980). *Metaphors we live by*. University of Chicago Press.
- Lakoff, G., & Johnson, M. (1999). *Philosophy in the flesh: The embodied mind and its challenge to western thought*. University of Chicago Press.
- Landau, M. J. (2018). Using metaphor to find meaning in life. *Review of General Psychology, 22*(1), 62-72. <http://doi.org/10.1037/gpr0000105>
- Landau, M. J., Oyserman, D., Keefer, L. A., & Smith, G. C. (2014). The college journey and academic engagement: How metaphor use enhances identity-based motivation. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology, 106*, 679-698. <http://doi.org/10.1037/a0036414>

- Lerman, C. L. (1991). On metaphoric communication as the original protolanguage. In von Raffler-Engel, W., Wind, J., & Jonker, A. (Eds.), *Studies in language origins* (Vol. 2). (pp. 245-262). John Benjamins.
- McCurry, S., and Hayes, S. C. (1992). Clinical and experimental perspectives on metaphorical talk. *Clinical Psychology Review, 12*:763-785. [http://doi.org/ 10.1016/0272-7358\(92\)90023-2](http://doi.org/10.1016/0272-7358(92)90023-2)
- Müller, C. (2017). Waking metaphors: Embodied cognition in multimodal discourse. In B. Hampe (Ed.), *Metaphor: Embodied cognition in discourse* (pp. 291–316). Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781108182324.017>
- Müller, C. (2019). Metaphorizing as embodied interactivity: What gesturing and film viewing can tell us about an ecological view on metaphor. *Metaphor and Symbol, 34*(1), 61-79. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10926488.2019.1591723>
- Oatley, K. (1999). Why fiction may be twice as true as fact: Fiction as cognitive and emotional simulation. *Review of General Psychology, 3*(2), 101-117. <https://doi.org/10.1037/1089-2680.3.2.101>
- Oatley, K. (2001). Shakespeare's invention of theater as simulation that runs on minds. *Empirical Studies of the Arts, 19*(1), 27-45. <https://doi.org/10.2190/H5DU-QEMY-JNHQ-MV8N>
- Oatley, K. (2016). Fiction: Simulation of social worlds. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences, 20*(8), 618-628. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2016.06.002>
- Ramírez, E. S., Ruiz, F. J., Peña-Vargas, A., & Bernal, P. A. (2021). Empirical investigation of the verbal cues involved in delivering experiential metaphors. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health, 18*(20), 10630. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph182010630>

- Ruiz, F. J., Luciano, C., & Sierra, M. A. (2020). A systematic and critical response to Pendrous et al. (2020) replication study. *Journal of Contextual Behavioral Science, 17*, 39-45.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcbs.2020.04.011>
- Sierra, M. A., Ruiz, F. J., Flórez, C. L., Riaño Hernández, D., & Luciano, C. (2016). The role of common physical properties and augmental functions in metaphor effect. *International Journal of Psychology & Psychological Therapy, 16*(3), 265-279.
- Skinner, B. F. (1945). The operational analysis of psychological terms. *Psychological Review, 52*(5), 270–277. <https://doi.org/10.1037/h0062535>
- Skinner, B. F. (1957). *Verbal behavior*. Appleton-Century-Crofts. <https://doi.org/10.1037/11256-000>
- Smith ADM & Höfler S (2017) From metaphor to symbols and grammar: the cumulative cultural evolution of language. In C. Power, M. Finnegan & H. Callan (Eds.), *Human Origins: contributions from social anthropology (Methodology & History in Anthropology, series 30)*. (pp. 153-179). Berghahn. <http://www.berghahnbooks.com/title/PowerHuman#toc>
- Stewart I., Barnes-Holmes D., Hayes S.C., Lipkens R. (2001) Relations among Relations: Analogies, Metaphors, and Stories. In S.C. Hayes, D. Barnes-Holmes & B. Roche (Eds.), *Relational Frame Theory. A post-skinnerian account of human language and cognition* (pp. 73-86). Kluwer Academic/Plenum Publishers. http://doi.org/10.1007/0-306-47638-X_4
- Stewart, I., & Barnes-Holmes, D. (2001). Understanding metaphor: A relational frame perspective. *The Behavior Analyst, 24*(2), 191-199. <http://doi.org/10.1007/BF03392030>
- Stewart, I., & Barnes-Holmes, D. (2004). Relational frame theory and analogical reasoning: Empirical investigations. *International Journal of Psychology and Psychological Therapy, 4*, 241-262.

- Stoddard, J. A., & Afari, N. (2014). *The big book of ACT metaphors: a practitioner's guide to experiential exercises and metaphors in Acceptance and Commitment Therapy*. New Harbinger Publications.
- Thibodeau PH & Boroditsky L (2011) Metaphors we think with: The role of metaphor in Reasoning. *PLoS ONE* 6(2): e16782. <http://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0016782>
- Thibodeau PH & Boroditsky L (2013) Natural language metaphors covertly influence reasoning. *PLoS ONE* 8(1): e52961. <http://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0052961>
- Thibodeau PH & Boroditsky L (2015) Measuring effects of metaphor in a dynamic opinion landscape. *PLoS ONE* 10(7): e0133939. <http://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0133939>
- Törneke, N. (2010). *Learning RFT: An introduction to relational frame theory and its clinical application*. New Harbinger Publications.
- Törneke, N. (2017). *Metaphor in practice: A professional's guide to using the science of language in psychotherapy*. New Harbinger Publications.
- Törneke, N. (2020). Strategies for using metaphor in psychological treatment. *Metaphor and the Social World*, 10(2), 214-232. <http://doi.org/10.1075/msw.00004.torç>
- Villatte, M., Villatte, J. L., & Monestès, J. (2014). Bypassing the traps of language with experiential practice. In: Stoddard, J. A., & Afari, N. (Eds.). *The Big Book of ACT Metaphors: a practitioner's guide to experiential exercises and metaphors in Acceptance and Commitment Therapy* (pp. 13-28). New Harbinger Publications.

Tables

Table 1. Characterisation and discourse examples of Theme 1. Life as variation, change, multiplicity.

Theme 1. Life as variation, change, multiplicity. Metaphors that focus on the recognition of variation in life, which has multiple and diverse aspects and in which changing events take place. These metaphors are conveyed by characteristics related to variation, diversity or change in a particular object or situation.

Theme 1 discourse examples (Life is a/an...)

...sky. Sometimes it is clear, with a bright blue, or with a rainbow that motivates you to carry out many projects, other times it is grey, which generates nostalgia and some uncertainty, but it always shines again (Participant 253, woman, 52 y.o., Venezuela).

...box of chocolates. You never know what you're going to get. In my opinion, the screenwriter of Forrest Gump was very right in this statement, because the only certainty we have is uncertainty. There are factors that you can control, but there are others that escape you and you will have to deal with them as they appear. Sometimes (life is) a very sweet white chocolate bonbon that you never want to end and sometimes a bitter one that you never want to take again, but that teaches you more than any other appetising one. (Participant 897, woman, 25 y.o., Spain)

...fruit. There are fruits of all flavours (Participant 1492, woman, 42 y.o., Colombia)

...meadow. In a meadow you have bad grass, good grass, different colours, pleasant perfumes and you can't choose, you can enjoy each space, or not, or just walk around... (Participant 1158, woman, 52 y.o., Argentina)

...wind. We arrived and without realising it we left very quickly (Participant 1145, woman, 64 y.o., Argentina)

Table 2. Characterisation, subthemes and discourse examples of Theme 2. Finding patterns within variation

Theme 2. Finding patterns within variation. Metaphors that recognise life's characteristics of change and transformation and that structure such variation by taking as a vehicle processes or actions that involve a beginning-development-end and/or where change is patterned/ordered. For example, life is understood as moving towards a destination or following a path, is equated with human or natural development, or is understood through analogy with works of fiction, games with rules and sports.

2.1. Life is movement or displacement from a current point to a destination. (Life is a/an...)

...journey by train. You get on (the train) as a baby, not knowing where you are going, along the way people get on who would give you their place if you need it, help you and support you; you grow as the train moves. Constantly there are those who get on and accompany you for a while, show you something and then leave when they reach their stop. Some enjoy the scenery and admire it; others, not knowing it and seeing how beautiful it is, envy it and may even damage it without thinking of the next ones who will get on the train to enjoy the journey. You discover love in some seat and sometimes that being will be your companion until the end of the journey or only in a few stations and so you keep on knowing, observing, learning and enjoying this wonderful journey". (Participant 363, woman, 34 y.o., Venezuela)

...marvellous journey. When you are born, it is your parents who form the path to follow and as an adolescent you begin to mark the differences to follow; It is up to you to continue on the right path or to make a mistake depending on the maturity you acquire for your own being and you enjoy the wonders that you find on this journey of life and if you encounter difficulties you overcome them and if it is difficult to overcome them you manage to overcome them with your own way forward, You always leave your footprints with love and without hurting, without mistreating, and you always find, as the years go by, that you have to reach a parking lot where you have to keep on fighting to reach your starting point for a new path. (Participant 1284, woman, 64 y.o., Nicaragua)

... journey. A journey has a beginning and an end, everything changes along the way: the people, the landscape, the situations... there are happy and sad moments, also difficult and pleasant. During the journey we also change ourselves, our way of seeing the landscape and of relating to people... at the end of the journey we are no longer the same as we were at the beginning (Participant 586, woman, 63 y.o., Venezuela).

... river. It moves forward, there are always new things, different things, it cannot go backwards, and it must go forward, every time it finds a stumbling block it overcomes it in different ways according to the situation (Participant 736, woman, 50 y.o., Argentina).

... journey. A journey in which the least important thing is where to get to. The most important thing in life is to enjoy what we have in each moment, without being obsessed with what we are going to do or what we have done. Even if we make plans for the future of what we want to achieve or where we want to go, that will only bring us well-being when we are in the moment, many times we will feel good even without having reached that goal (Participant 64, man, 25 y.o., Spain).

2.2. Life as a process of human or natural development (Life is a/an...)

... school. As you advance and complete your tasks, you gain more knowledge and the next levels become easier. If you don't do your homework and you don't pass, you will remain at the same level and every day more responsibilities will accumulate that will make it more difficult for you to advance and, as time goes by, you will lose strength, but the greater your motivation, (the more) it will help you to overcome the obstacles. There will also be many teachers and classmates who will help you, or hinder your progress, with the difference that many of them you will be able to choose or reject according to your criteria and your maturity. Many will choose you as a partner and others will also reject you. Your success or failure will depend on who you choose and who chooses you. These are some of the comparisons that exist between life and school. I could cite more, but these are the ones that stand out and come to mind now (Participant 1073, woman, 55 y.o., Venezuela).

...opportunity. It is an opportunity to learn, to grow, to develop skills and knowledge, to acquire spiritual values, love (Participant 533, woman, 61 y.o., Argentina).

...tree. We grow, we become strong, we shed our leaves and wither but we blossom again. There are trees that when they are felled grow again, just as we all hit rock bottom and we get back up again (Participant 1373, woman,

28 y.o., Argentina).

... Moon. The Moon presents different phases and there is always an unknown part, and in the end, we can see it between sighs of nostalgia for the phases that have already passed and we rejoice with the phases to come. But always waiting to discover that unknown part that finally unveils its mysteries (Participant 1484, woman, 66 y.o., Mexico).

...seed. Life is like a seed, which is planted from the moment we are born, and from there it takes special care, with which we are formed as human beings; as the seed grows, we take into account that we ourselves are the ones who decide to take care of it or damage it, each one decides; in my case, I decided to take care of it, to give it the most human and free form possible, to give my life a great importance for me and an importance to those around me, to give my opinions in a more special way, and not just to say, but to transmit an emotion. I LOVE LIFE because God created it, I see beauty and beauty in everything, emotions, nature, everything intangible, there is God, taking care of us. God is life, our seed is God, who helps us to grow and value ourselves". (Participant 120, woman, 18 y.o., Colombia)

2.3. Understanding life through fiction or games and sports (Life is a/an...)

...book. Each chapter is different, some are exciting, others emotional, others sad, some predictable and others surprising, full of characters that enrich each experience but it is the protagonist who directs and gives meaning to the story that can only be known if one advances page by page (Participant 118, woman, 40 y.o., Spain).

...film. It is a film because it is based on a script that is written by ourselves in collaboration with the people around us (Participant 609, woman, 22 y.o., Colombia).

...video game. We have different obstacles to overcome, which will allow us to advance. Also in the games, if you have a lot of money you can buy items that will make your way easier... and when you die you lose the game, if you haven't reached the final level, everything you've done makes no sense... (Participant 289, woman, 20 y.o., Honduras)

...chess game. Life is like a chess game, because every day we make decisions, every step we take has a consequence, sometimes we lose and sometimes we win, but we always learn from our mistakes and try again. Every move we make leads to a different result (Participant 182, man, 19 y.o., Nicaragua).

...game. (Life is a game) because we all want to win more, however we have to be cautious (strategists) to achieve the goal and every decision has a consequence either good or bad (Participant 366, man, 22 y.o., Nicaragua).

Table 3. Characterisation, subthemes and discourse examples of Theme 3. Variation in life as a problem

Theme 3. Variation in life as a problem. Metaphors that focus on the problematic aspects of variation and change in life, such as the absence of clear purpose, the occurrence of unpredictable or random events, the agent's lack of control, and the more destructive/chaotic aspects associated with change, such as conflict and isolation/separation

3.1. Lack of purpose (*Life is a/an...*)

...a labyrinth. Life is like a labyrinth. A labyrinth is complicated. In a labyrinth you can always go left or right, but you will never know which is the right choice until you have made a decision, and sometimes even after that you don't know if it was the right decision, because you can't know what you are going to face next. A labyrinth is about making decision after decision about which way to go, which direction is right, which path is the right one; in a labyrinth you need to make many decisions hoping that you will be lucky to choose the right path and not end up in front of a dead end, because there can always be a dead end around the corner, while you have to carry forever the doubt and the fear that at some point you will have to turn back because of a bad decision, not knowing how far you will have to turn back, and carrying the weight of all that you have invested to get there, which now turns out to have been in vain. Life is a labyrinth, life is too complicated. Life is making decisions under the assumption that you know what you are doing. Life is continually risking being wrong. Life is the fear of knowing that you are going to hit a wall at a dead end but having no idea when or what the consequences will be. Life is wandering lost and aiming in an unknown direction under the self-imposed lie that we know what we are doing so as not to collapse under the crushing pressure of uncertainty that we strive to deny, until at some point it decides to take its toll and we realise that we were never sure of anything, nor are we, and that although we could have done worse, we could also have done much better. Life is like a labyrinth, a labyrinth that nobody likes, even if nobody wants to admit it." (Participant 459, man, 19 y.o., Venezuela)

...prison. Life is like a prison. There are good days where you can eat good food. There are bad days where you get beaten up by someone else to drain their problems. There are days where you feel a certain freedom despite being caged. There are days where you just want to escape from that cage even though you know that's what you deserve. There are highs and lows but there are times where they are more lows than highs (Participant 902, woman, 18 y.o., Venezuela).

...carousel. (Life is) a carousel because we go round and round, we go up and down, we cry and laugh (Participant 266, woman, 51 y.o., Venezuela).

...meaningless story. I think life doesn't really have any meaning, we are all Sisyphus pushing a stone over a mountain again and again (Participant 571, man, 19 y.o., Guatemala)

...a tunnel. (Life is) a dark and cruel tunnel to go through with no option to find the way out, no option to find the light at the end. It's too hard; not for everyone, for some people life is very fair (but) for others it's a bitch (Participant 1291, woman, 38 y.o., Nicaragua).

3.2. Randomness and unpredictability (*Life is a/an...*)

...roller coaster. The roller coaster goes up and down just like your state of mind, one day you may be at the top and the next you may be at the bottom, also every turn you don't know what awaits you, whether it's a bad experience that leaves you with a great life lesson or just an experience that doesn't fulfil you, for me that's what life is like. (Participant 770, woman, 27 y.o., Mexico)

...set of random events. Life is like a set of random events that lead us in one way or another to suffering, whether it is the break-up of a relationship, an accident, the death of a family member, and if you think about it, that is life, full of many moments of suffering, and although we have many moments of happiness, these are ephemeral, once the happiness is over, we return to the daily routine of life, and we have to face this suffering in the best way, since it makes us grow as people, and be able to be free. (Participant 470, man, 20 y.o., Colombia)

...weathercock. (Life is a weathercock) because it takes unsuspected directions (Participant 436, woman, 37 y.o., Colombia)

...lottery game. You never know what is going to happen on a day to day basis (Participant 1485, woman, 44 y.o., Venezuela)

...wheel of fortune. Life is like a wheel of fortune, because with a new day comes new events. One day you can find yourself at the top of the wheel, feeling at peace with yourself, happy, energetic and at the top of your game (in various aspects), but the next day you can find yourself at the bottom of the wheel, feeling unhappy, sad and even losing everything you value. The secret is in the attitude to face each level (Participant 273, woman, 22 y.o., Nicaragua).

3.3 Life as enigmatic or unknowable (*Life is a/an...*)

...riddle. When you manage to find the answers (in life), everything makes sense; as long as you can't, frustration and anxiety will be a big obstacle to continue (Participant 65, woman, 22 y.o., Colombia).

...mirror room. It is complicated to understand and no matter how much we look outside for answers, everything we see is nothing more than our interpretation of reality. This makes some days very sad and others very happy. In the end, there will always be more questions than answers (Participant 779, woman, 24 y.o., Venezuela).

...novel (fictional writing). Everything (in life) is a plot that cannot be understood in the end. (Participant 1125, woman, 57 y.o., Venezuela)

3.4. Lack of control (*Life is a/an...*)

...bad joke. I mean, besides having to accept living against my will from the day of my birth, I should be grateful for all the bad things that may happen to me...because it is an experience, a lesson of growth...! Fuck it, why should I be grateful that life is so difficult? Is it a fucking joke? (Participant 730, woman, 21 y.o., Colombia)

...roller coaster. I feel inside a carousel with no control to choose direction, speed, companion, with emotional surprises and at vertigo speed in some moments. (Participant 990, woman, 52 y.o., Spain)

...puppet theatre. We are managed, we don't know our next step (Participant 1329, woman, 69 y.o., Colombia)

...raffle. Some people try very hard and don't get the results they expect, while others are rewarded without so much effort (Participant 1155, woman, 72 y.o., Argentina)

3.5. Destruction, Conflict, Isolation/Separation and Chaos (*Life is a/an...*)

...party to which I have not been invited. I don't feel at ease in any situation or with any person (Participant 756, man, 54 y.o., Argentina)

...jungle. We have to identify whether we are the prey or the predator. In a world where power, money, your race, your gender and your nationality are the main factors that determine your position or status (Participant 633, woman, 19 y.o., Venezuela)

...boxing match. Blow after blow and you have to get up again. Like this until the end (Participant 1538, woman, 26 y.o., Argentina)

...war. Life is a war because you win and lose, because you are in constant change and struggle (Participant 86, woman, 22 y.o., Mexico).

...coming storm. As you get older, you realise that you are walking into a big black cloud that gets bigger and darker and you enter a state of confusion whether to move on or stay where you are (Participant 200, woman, 24 y.o., Costa Rica).

Table 4. Characterisation, subthemes and discourse examples of Theme 4. Evaluating life.

Theme 4. Metaphors that are conveyed through the appetitive or aversive qualities of certain specific objects or situations and that transmit a positive or negative evaluation of life.

4.1. Positive evaluations (Life is a/an...)

...strawberry. I like strawberries. (Participant 80, woman, 21 y.o., Ecuador)

...gift/present. Life is like a gift. It is something that we earn without merit, that comes to us the way it comes to us and that is how we have to live and enjoy it (Participant 401, woman, 42 y.o., Argentina).

...wonder/miracle. From the moment we are born we are filled with gifts and blessings. People who are angels appear in our lives, some love us, some guide us, some help us and the surprise of seeing the sunlight at each sunrise is wonderful. The possibility of doing new things, of using our gifts, of projecting ourselves and serving others, of developing a vocation are gifts of energy. And even when we have dark days or dark nights, there is always a hope or a miracle. Only those who stop believing it fail. God is love (Participant 672, woman, 66 y.o., Guatemala).

...treasure. (Life is a) treasure not to be squandered. I think people live with the mentality of having greatness, of being determined to get rich and live a dissolute life, and they waste their lives trying to get it. They don't stop for a moment to meditate, to ask themselves what they really want to do with their precious lives. It's not wrong to want to be financially stable but when you focus too much on getting comfort and wealth sometimes you miss what life is really about. Having a family, values and education according to your personality. Because in the end when you die you will not be called "Dr. so and so" or "Graduate so and so", but who you really were as a person. An honest man, a loyal friend, a loving husband, and that is where you know that you really treasured your life and did not waste it on paper that remains just that: paper" (Participant 261, woman, 25 y.o., Venezuela).

4.2. Negative evaluations (Life is a/an...)

...rainy day. On a rainy day it is dangerous to go out, you feel vulnerable, you are cold, you get sick, nobody stops to cover you up, you just want to go home. (Participant 855, woman, 31 y.o., Costa Rica)

...meaningless thing. (Life) has no meaning for me. (Participant 1202, woman, 24 y.o., Venezuela)

...a very difficult thing. (Life) is very difficult. (Participant 1320, woman, 51 y.o., Mexico)

...a dog poo. Life is like dog poo because so many demands are placed on you and if you don't deliver you are labelled a failure.(Participant 206, woman, 33 y.o., Venezuela)

...pizza. The pizza box is a square, the pizza is round and the slice is triangular (It does not make sense). (Participant 1229, woman, 22 y.o., Mexico)

Figure captions.

Figure 1. Thematic map of metaphors about life

